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TOOLS, METHODS AND METHODS OF TEACHING TECHNICAL SKILLS IN BASKETBALL TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the tools, methods and techniques used in the process of teaching technical skills in basketball training. The study highlights the importance of modern pedagogical approaches in the process of teaching the main elements of game technique - passing, receiving, dribbling, hitting and defensive movements. It also examines the effectiveness of visual aids, repetitive exercises, game methods, and individual and group work methods in training. The article also provides innovative approaches and practical recommendations that serve to improve the technical training of basketball players.

Keywords: basketball, technical skills, training, methodology, teaching methods, dribbling, passing, hitting, game method, sports training.

INTRODUCTION

Basketball is one of the most popular and rapidly developing sports in the world today. This sport requires not only high physical activity, but also develops quick thinking, strategic decision-making and teamwork skills. Therefore, basketball requires excellent technical training from athletes.

Technical skills are the basis of the game of basketball. Accurate passing of the ball, correct reception, effective dribbling, shooting and mastery of defensive movements directly affect the outcome of the game. Therefore, teaching technical elements in the training process is one of the important pedagogical tasks.

The process of forming technical skills in basketball players is complex and multi-stage, requiring the use of various tools, methods and techniques. Since each

player has individual characteristics, the training process should also be organized on the basis of an adapted approach.

In modern sports pedagogy, innovative methods, interactive exercises, visual aids and digital technologies are widely used to improve technical training. This serves to increase students' interest in the training and make the learning process more effective.

The process of teaching technical elements in basketball training includes not only performing physical exercises, but also correctly analyzing and improving movements. Therefore, the pedagogical skills and methodological approach of coaches are important.

Also, repeated exercises, training close to game situations, and team training play an important role in the formation of technical skills in students. This process develops the ability of athletes to make quick decisions and act correctly on the court.[1]

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The sustainable development of independent Uzbekistan and its emergence among the economically and socially advanced countries is directly related, first of all, not only to the level of education and intellectual potential of the younger generation and the working-age population, but also to their physical health and well-being. Therefore, improving the system of continuous education, improving the quality of education, and training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the requirements of the modern labor market are among the important tasks of today.

In accordance with the tasks set out in the resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-197 dated May 28, 2024 and No. PQ-221 dated July 8, 2025, special attention is paid to educating students not only in the educational process, but also in educating them as fully developed, spiritually and physically well-rounded individuals.

Physical education and sports are an integral part of the culture of society and play an important role in the formation of a healthy lifestyle and ensuring the physical development of every citizen. At the same time, in the process of educating the younger generation in the spirit of the national idea, it is important to strengthen their health, develop mental stability, and form the need for a healthy lifestyle.[2]

Today, the development of physical education and sports is closely related to the socio-economic development of Uzbekistan and has become one of the priority areas of state policy. During the years of independence, extensive work has been carried out to attract the population, especially children and youth, to sports.

At the present stage, the issue of improving the physical fitness of students in secondary schools and sports schools and developing their motor skills is relevant. This

process also has a positive effect on the future professional activities of young people, since early motor skills serve as an important basis for later mastering complex sports or professional activities.

In the process of physical education, it is necessary to take into account the individual characteristics, health and physical capabilities of each student. Otherwise, the wrong approach can negatively affect health and reduce the effectiveness of training. Therefore, physical education is considered an important pedagogical process that forms a conscious attitude towards one's own body in students, develops willpower and moral qualities.

Purposeful organization and careful planning of the educational process are one of the main factors determining the effectiveness of physical education. The formation of a positive attitude towards sports in students directly depends on the pedagogical approach, methods and skills of the teacher.[3]

Modern basketball is one of the fastest developing sports today, and its technical and tactical capabilities have significantly expanded. Complex movements, rapid exchanges and high physical loads during the game require a high level of training from athletes.

In recent decades, the content of basketball has changed significantly. Game techniques, tactical combinations, tricks and quick decision-making processes have become much more complex. This requires athletes to improve their physical, technical and psychological preparation to a higher level.

At the same time, changes in competition rules and increased competition require players to develop quick adaptability, strategic thinking and the ability to make the right decisions in various game situations.

At the current stage of basketball development, it is important to improve the training system from young athletes to the professional level. In this regard, ensuring the inextricable link between technical, tactical and physical training is the main task.

In general, physical education and sports, in particular basketball, serve as an important tool in shaping the younger generation as healthy, active and spiritually mature individuals.

Figure 1. Position of a basketball player holding the ball

There are several important basic principles in the player's activity, which include the ability to feel the partner, develop peripheral vision, predict the situation in advance and calculate.[5]

I. Feeling the partner. The player who passes the ball must constantly be aware of the location of his partners on the field, their physical capabilities and psychological state. In this process, each player's speed, ball reception skills, activity in attack and defense, reaction to feints, ability to play under the shield and throwing technique are important.

II. Peripheral vision. The player who passes the ball must not only look in one direction, but also be able to control the situation around him. He must develop peripheral vision to such a level that he can perceive the actions taking place on the 180-degree field. Through training, the skill of controlling the situation on the field 360 degrees is formed, while turning the head to a minimum.

III. Anticipation. A good player can predict the further development of the game even before receiving the ball. He has the ability to anticipate the movements of his teammates and opponents and deliver the ball to the right place and at the right time.

IV. Calculation. This is the skill of making decisions based on intuition and perception. The player must be able to determine when and how to pass the ball (high, low, straight or deflected), which teammate is in a favorable position and in which situations it is not advisable to pass the ball. He also assesses the strengths and weaknesses of the opponents' defense and executes each pass in accordance with the specific situation.

Coach's recommendations. For taller players, these exercises may be difficult at first, so they are taught in stages: first walking, then light jogging, and then at speed. If it is difficult to perform the exercise in full, it is recommended to perform it on a smaller part of the field. During the training, it is emphasized that players should focus on the court, not the ball. It is recommended to perform these exercises regularly, for 30–60 seconds.[6]

CONCLUSION

Today, modern methods are widely used in the process of teaching basketball, along with traditional methods. This helps to make the learning process more effective and interesting and develops the technical skills of athletes faster.

In general, teaching the basics of technique and tactics in basketball training plays an important role in the formation of children's physical development, coordination of movements and teamwork skills. The gradual mastery of technical elements and the use of age-appropriate tactical methods increase students' interest in sports and improve their performance. In addition, systematic and planned training serves to develop discipline, responsibility and a spirit of competition in children.

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